

Effect of prevailing temperature and humidity on rice armyworm reproduction during upland crop season

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Rice armyworm *Mythimna loreyi* (Dup.) migrates from rice to other cereal crops in areas where multiple cropping is the practice and climatic variations are extreme. In North India, it attacks rice Jun-Nov, then migrates to wheat, barley, sugarcane, oat, and napier Dec-May.

To study the effect of prevailing Dec-May temperature and humidity on its reproductive biology, we used adults from the mass culture raised in the

laboratory at 26±1 °C in BOD incubators. Each month, 15 freshly emerged pairs (male + female) were released separately in glass jars (15 × 10 cm) with muslin cloth covers. Dry sugarcane leaves kept in jars for egg laying were renewed daily after initiation of oviposition. A sucrose solution (10%)-soaked cotton swab provided for feeding.

Females always survived longer (4.5-21.2 d) than males (4.0-11.0 d) (see table). In spite of a longer oviposition period (10-11 d) during Dec-Jan, females laid fewer eggs (75-95 eggs/female) and more infertile ones because of low temperature. Rising temperatures (9-26 °C) in Feb enhanced fecundity and hatching. During Mar (12-32 °C) and Apr (18-36 °C),

temperature considerably reduced the oviposition period (4-5 d) compared to Dec-Jan (10-11 d) but increased fecundity about 3 times, with 29.4-42.4% hatching. Average daily egg output was also higher during Feb-Apr than during Dec-Jan. In May, high temperature (24-42 °C) significantly reduced adult longevity and fecundity. Eggs laid in May did not hatch.

In December and March relative humidity was almost the same, indicating its insignificant role. During the experimental period, however, optimum conditions (25-30 °C and 75-85% RH) never prevailed, resulting in poor overall fecundity and egg viability. It appears that rice armyworm reproduction is most affected by temperature. □

Effect of prevailing temperature and humidity on reproductive activity of rice armyworm adults.^a Hisar, India.

Month	Temperature (°C)		Relative humidity (%)	Pre-oviposition period (d)	Oviposition period (d)	Postoviposition period (d)	Adult longevity (d)		Eggs (no./female)	Eggs (no./d)	Incubation period (d)	Hatching (%)
	Max	Min					Male	Female				
Dec	18±2.3	8±1.5	59±5.2	10.0	10.0	1.0	10.0	21.0	75	7.5	—	—
Jan	20±2.1	6±2.4	70±4.5	9.8	11.0	0.5	9.0	21.2	95	8.6	—	—
Feb	26±2.8	9±3.0	57±4.0	6.5	5.5	1.2	11.0	13.0	320	58.2	7.5	22.6
Mar	32±2.9	12±3.0	57±3.5	5.0	5.0	2.0	8.0	12.0	253	50.6	5.0	42.4
Apr	36±2.0	18±2.4	45±2.8	3.0	4.0	1.0	5.5	8.0	276	69.0	4.6	29.4
May	42±4.0	24±3.0	36±3.0	3.0	1.0	0.5	4.0	4.5	15	15.0	—	—
LSD (0.05)				2.4	1.6	0.6	2.3	3.4	56	13.5	1.3	10.6

^aAv of 15 replications, 1 pair (female + male) of adults/replication.

Chemical control of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* has become a major pest in both dry and wet season rice in western Orissa. Peak activity during booting causes high yield loss.

We evaluated seven insecticides for WBPH control in the field, in a randomized block design with three replications. Jaya seedlings (35 d old) were transplanted 9 Feb 1987 at 15- × 20-cm spacing in 20-m² plots.

Effect of some insecticides on WBPH population in summer rice. Sambalpur, Orissa, India, 1987.

Insecticide ^a	Formulation	Dose (kg ai/ha)	WBPH population/hill ^b		Grain yield (t/ha)
			69 DT	74 DT	
Chlorpyrifos	10 G	1.0	96.6	48.5	5.1
Ethoprofos	10 G	1.5	137.1	44.8	5.9
Cartap	4 G	1.5	19.3	5.2	6.4
Carbofuran	3 G	1.0	2.5	1.9	6.8
Chlorpyrifos	40 EC	0.5	89.1	11.6	5.3
Decamethrin + buprofezin	5.9 EC	0.09	29.1	7.4	5.6
Phosalone	35 EC	0.5	65.5	33.1	5.3
No insecticide	—	—	109.3	97.3	5.0
LSD (0.05)			48.8	21.7	0.4

^aApplied at 20 and 70 DT. ^bMean of 10 hills.

Insecticides were applied 20 and 70 d after transplanting (DT).

Except for WBPH, no other pests appeared in appreciable numbers. WBPH population was counted at peak

activity and 1 d before and 3 d after the second insecticide application.

At 69 DT, as many as 109 WBPH/ hill were counted in check plots (see table). Carbofuran-treated plots had